

BioWood

D1.4: Potential land use management scenarios, based on recent trends, policy developments and socio-economic trends

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Introduction

The circular bio-economy promotes the use of renewable bio-resources such as wood, and their conversion into chemical building blocks, biofuels, feed and food via biorefinery technologies. Bio-based industries are a significant subsector of the bio-economy, and a strong bio-based industrial sector helps to reduce Europe's dependency on fossil-based products (Palahí et al., 2020). Sustainable forest management combined with sustainable wood conversion and use has a large potential to contribute to the circular bio-economy, where products are re-used and recycled through cascade use as long as possible (Weber-Blaschke & Muys, 2020; Navare et al., 2022). Nevertheless, an integrated Flemish let alone European bio-based industry sector does not exist yet, and therefore the bio-economy includes a wide range of different subsectors often working in isolation. This lack of value chains and the missing support for their development hampers growth of the biobased industry in Flanders and the EU.

The primary aim of BioWood is to support the development of a new wood-based value chain in Flanders. Reaching this goal relies on an integration of a sustainable wood supply and a feasible conversion process towards unique high-value bio-based products. To that end, a major scientific challenge related to the first component, i.e. supply of woody biomass, is the development of a reliable methodology for assessing its current and future availability in Flanders.

The Sim4Tree tool (Dalemans et al., 2015) can serve as a basis for tackling this challenge but is, in its current state, unable to making sufficiently accurate assessments of future biomass availability. Updating the tool with (i) more recent yield tables and (ii) land-cover maps, (iii) ecological and technical restrictions for biomass harvesting, (iv) scaling factors adjusting for productivity changes due to climate change and (v) inclusion of different land-use scenarios are necessary to make accurate predictions on future biomass availability.

The goal of this deliverable is to design a set of 15 integrated scenarios that combine land use change, climate change and forest management to predict the availability of woody biomass for the coming 30 years (2020-2050). The scenarios are based on five existing land use change scenarios for Flanders, developed in previous studies (Engelen *et al.*, 2011a; Engelen *et al.*, 2011b; Michels *et al.*, 2018), with three associated management scenarios and two climate change scenarios. The land use change scenarios account for a range of social, political and economic trends that influence the future land use practices, changing the forest area and its management goals (see also section 1.1). A first scenario considers the land use changes under "business as usual" practices. Two other scenarios focus on a more nature-based perspective and the last two scenarios are more production-based. The forest management scenarios were defined following either a business-as-usual, a nature-oriented or a production-oriented mindset. These five scenario combinations are simulated under current climate conditions and subsequently replicated under two representative concentration pathways, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5. Along the process of scenario design, the code of the Sim4Tree DSS was updated so that it is capable of handling these scenarios for estimation of supply potential of woody biomass. This deliverable D1.4 is one of the nine reports composed for this project:

- **D1.1:** License agreement between ANB-Naturinvest (owner) and Forecoman-LandInforMan (licensee) on the further development of the Sim4Tree software
- **D1.2:** Selection of existing growth models relevant for Flanders
- **D1.3:** Model- and species-specific scaling factors to account for impacts of global environmental change on growth/net annual increment of trees

- ***D1.4: Potential land use management scenarios, based on recent trends, policy developments and socio-economic trends***
- **D1.5:** Set of correction factors to take into account legal, technical and ecological criteria for harvest of different biomass fractions
- **D1.6:** Refined high resolution land use map for Flanders, related to woody biomass production in forests and linking appropriate attributes and production models
- **D1.9:** Analysis and interpretation of wood harvest simulations in Flanders until 2050
- **M1.1:** Development of a BioWood-DSS by upgrading of the Sim4Tree DSS
- **M1.2:** Application of the Biowood DSS to simulate the wood resource evolution in Flanders until 2050 under different socio-economic scenarios

1 Land use change scenarios

1.1 Scenario selection

As part of a broader exercise relating to visions for the future land use in the Flemish Region of Belgium, VITO prepared **four world views** in 2011, based on different policy developments and socioeconomic trends (Figure 1). These world views reflect, in both qualitative and quantitative terms, the possible land use changes over time until 2050. They were constructed regarding various themes such as demographics, employment, energy, mobility, environment, space, nature, water and agriculture (Engelen *et al.*, 2011a). To obtain a reference, the “business as usual” (BAU) land use scenario was selected from the ‘Ruimtelijk-Dynamisch Landgebruiksmodel voor Vlaanderen’ (Engelen *et al.*, 2011b), which describes the spatial development of Flanders for the period 2010-2050 as a result of ongoing population growth and employment dynamics and projected allocation of space for nature and agriculture. Two other ‘Flanders world views’ or land use change scenarios were selected: (i) “Strong Europe” (SE) with a strong regulatory role of the European Union and a focus on nature conservation goals and (ii) “Transatlantic Markets” (TA) with minimal attention for environmental quality and nature conservation or development while the area of production forest is increased significantly. Additionally, two land use change predictions were chosen from the NARA (NatuurRApporten) project (Michels *et al.*, 2018): (i) “Stimulating the economy” (NARA3) considers nature as a valuable resource for generating income while (ii) “Cooperation with nature” (NARA4) focuses on the sustainable use of the natural resources. These reports can also be visited through the webpage of the INBO: <https://www.vlaanderen.be/inbo/inbo-natuurrapporten/>. The five land use change scenarios for the observed period are summarised in table 1. These five scenarios were selected from an available set of several other previously constructed scenarios because they were considered most relevant to examine from a forest management point of view. For example, both NARA1 (Cultural identity) and NARA3 (Flow of the economy) are expecting an increase of 10 000 ha forest. We choose to select NARA3 and not NARA1 because in NARA3 the locations of expected afforestation were based on AGNAS (Delineation of Natural and Agricultural Structures Areas), which are more likely to be executed and therefore advantageous to be taken into account in future afforestation. By considering scenarios with different visions (production- and nature-oriented, business as usual), a wide range of possible developments and subsequently expected biomass production can thus be assessed.

Figure 1: The axes of the Welfare and Environment study and the 4 resulting world views adapted from the extensive report by Engelen *et al.* (2011a).

1.1.1 Business-as-usual

The business as usual (BAU) land use change scenario is used in the current study as the reference scenario indicating how land use will possibly evolve in the coming years if current trends proceed. The controlling factors for the scenario include prognoses of population growth, of employment in the 12 economic sectors, and of the space occupied by agriculture and nature (Engelen *et al.*, 2011a).

1.1.2 Strong Europe

The Strong Europe (SE) scenario is based on a world view developed by VITO where European integration of member states occurs, and the EU acts strongly and united in a regulatory way for agricultural, environmental, nature, energy and transport policy and for spatial planning. For Flanders SE considers population growth through economic migration, densifying cities with new residential areas at their edges. Nature areas are expanding as a result of government policy aimed at conserving and even enhancing biodiversity, partly driven by EU regulations.

1.1.3 Transatlantic markets

The Transatlantic Markets (TA) scenario is based on a world view in which private initiative and individual freedom strongly determine economic development. Immigration is restricted and the population remains more or less constant. A high degree of social inequality arises, with the richer part of the population living in the urban margins or in the countryside. Energy needs are met through fossil fuels and nuclear energy. Attention to the environment is limited and the quality of the environment is declining. There is little attention for biodiversity conservation and nature areas are mainly devoted to production forests that provide income from wood.

1.1.4 Stimulating the economy

'Harnessing the flow of the economy' (NARA3) scenario is one of the four perspectives in the nature exploration reports (Michels *et al.*, 2018). In this scenario, nature is a valuable resource to generate income. This can be done, for example by producing food or wood, by providing space for recreation or by making commercial areas more attractive to employees by including green elements or small forest patches. The green infrastructure is owned by companies and individuals, with access to be paid.

1.1.5 Cooperation with nature

The last scenario is 'Cooperate with nature' (NARA4), which underlines the mutual dependence of humans and nature. Natural processes are important for quality of life and prosperity whereby humans use natural resources in a sustainable way, in order to remain available for the next generations. Green infrastructure is deliberately constructed to optimize natural processes where functional biodiversity prevails. Nature policy ensures the preservation and restoration of species that contribute to the desired ecosystem functions in society. Cities are characterized by an interconnected green-blue network and the role of government in coordinating actions and stimulating participatory decisions and projects for sustainability, is important.

Table 1: The five different land use change scenarios are presented here, showing the main differences between the reference (business as usual) scenario, the two nature oriented scenarios and the two productivity oriented scenarios. SPA = special protection areas

Scenarios	Scenario target by 2050	Assumptions	Conversions
Business as usual (BAU)	+13 000 ha forest	Continue current trends	
Strong Europe (SE)	+50% forest with nature management -25% forest with production oriented forest management.	EU2020 agenda: more nature that is not forest with focus on nature conservation rather than production	
Transatlantic Markets (TA)	-50% forest with nature management +18% forest with forest management.	Because of economic interests: more production forest	
Stimulate the economy as primary purpose (NARA3)	+10 000 ha forest	Spatially connecting current forests Achieve EU targets of SPA's Afforestation in urban areas	
Cooperation with nature (NARA4)	+ 20 000 ha forest	Achieve EU targets of SPA's Buffering residential zones against noise Afforestation in urban areas	

1.2 Combining the land use change scenarios with the initial forest situation

The five land use change scenarios (three VITO world views and the two NARA land use change maps) were provided in different data formats. The VITO world views are composed of a stack of maps with 10 years interval starting with 2010 until 2050 while the NARA reports describe a start (2013) and end (2050) situation, all in a raster (.tiff) format. In addition, the VITO world views and the NARA reports initially start from a different forest map. However, it is required that all scenarios are complementary and start from the same initial forest situation. Therefore, a new forest map, developed for BioWood, was implemented and is explained more extensively in Lopez *et al.* (2020). This new map is a forest cover map with comparable forest area as indicated by the Boswijzer 2016 and based on the forest definition applied by ANB.

Starting with a new uniform base map for each of the five scenarios meant that some mismatches with the land use change scenarios had to be resolved: First, forest covered regions in the base map (D 1.6) which did not correspond to a forest land use type in the initial state of the land use change scenario were all considered as forest, causing an increase in the initial forested area of the scenarios. Second, regions which according to the scenarios are to be afforested in the period 2020 – 2050 and which were already considered forest in the base map remained under the forest class. However, this meant that for some scenarios, the afforested area was lower than specified by the scenario. Finally, regions which were not considered forest in the base map and which were to be deforested according to the scenarios were considered to have been deforested prior to 2020. This translates into a smaller deforested area between 2020 – 2050. The total forest area, afforested land and deforested land in our scenarios thus slightly differed from the proposed scenarios by Engelen *et al.*, (2011a), Engelen *et al.*, (2011b) and Michels *et al.*, (2018) (Table 2).

Table 2: Numerical values for the five land use change scenarios adjusted for a start from the 2020 forest map resulting in "real" afforestation and deforestation amounts defined by the land use changes.

Scenarios	Source	Simulation	Timeframe	Forest area 2020 (ha)	Forest area 2050 (ha)	Afforestation (ha)	Deforestation (ha)
BAU	VITO	4 world views 2012	2020-2050	162703	175395	13312	620

SE	VITO	4 world views 2012			160465	16326	18564
TA	VITO	4 world views 2012			185516	29113	6300
NARA3	INBO	NARA 2018			171883	13966	4786
NARA4	INBO	NARA 2018			179259	21761	5205

Sim4Tree is a simulation tool and decision support system working on a 5-year cycle, corresponding with the intervention times considered in the updated empirical tree growth tables available for Flanders (Storms *et al.* 2020). However, the three world view scenarios from VITO (S1, S2 and S3) worked in a 10-year cycle. To cope with this difference in temporal resolution, afforestation and deforestation within these 10 years were randomly allocated to one of two 5-year cycles, fitting the cycles of the Sim4Tree tool. The NARA scenarios (NARA3 and NARA4) were available for the initial year (2020) and the final year (2050) only. The area to be afforested or deforested was therefore equally distributed over the six 5-year intervals and the exact locations (pixels) were randomly chosen from all the pixels to be afforested and deforested in the 30-year period. The total forest area for each time interval for each of the scenarios is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Estimated Flemish forest area evolution (ha) following five land use change scenarios interpolated into 5-year time steps

Scenarios	Timestep 0 (2020)	Timestep 1 (2025)	Timestep 2 (2030)	Timestep 3 (2035)	Timestep 4 (2040)	Timestep 5 (2045)	Timestep 6 (2050)
BAU (S1)	162703	166700	170696	172049	173401	174397	175395
SE (S2)		167091	171472	169167	166866	163665	160463
TA (S3)		168147	173596	177149	180703	183113	185516
NARA3 (S4)		164234	165765	167291	168825	170354	171883
NARA4 (S5)		165459	168213	170972	173735	176495	179259

2 Forest management scenarios

Three management scenarios are defined for the forests present in each of the land use change scenarios, i.e. BAU, nature- and production-oriented management. This leads to a total of five scenarios where the LUC scenarios are combined with the management scenarios as follows: BAU – BAU management (S1), SE – Nature management (S2), TA – Production management (S3), NARA3 – Production management (S4) and NARA4 – Nature management (S5). The management scenarios differ in rotation time and species selection for regeneration after felling. BAU represents the current forest management of the Flemish region, while Nature and Production is based on the case studies of increased biodiversity resp. increased harvests for bioenergy as published by Härkönen et al. (2019). A general overview of the management scenarios is provided in Table 4. More details about the terminology of Table 4 is provided in the upcoming paragraphs.

Table 4: An overview of the three selected management scenarios.

	BAU	Nature	Production
Rotation length	Standard Sim4Tree	Standard Sim4Tree + 25% OR the maximum length of the yield table	Until time of maximum mean annual increment (MAI) of the volume
Priorities for regeneration	Coniferous forests are being converted to mixed deciduous stands when the rotation time is reached, meaning deciduous species receive a higher priority. The species preference of regeneration is native species, rather than non-native species.	Only native species are allowed which belong to the potential natural vegetation (PNV) of Flanders. Nature strives for tree species diverse forests.	The focus is placed on economically important species for Flanders, such as <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> and <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> .
Principle of regeneration*	Species suitability to the soil and regeneration priority	Species suitability to the soil and regeneration priority	Species productivity on the soil and regeneration priority
Stand-still principle**	Yes	Yes	Yes
Exclusion of non-native species	No	Yes	No

* The principle of regeneration determines which species will have a higher chance of being selected for regeneration. Users can define their own regeneration priorities (e.g. beech is preferred over Scots pine) and/or give a higher preference to certain species based on predefined criteria (soil suitability or species productivity).

** The stand-still principle states that native species cannot be replaced by non-native species and that deciduous species cannot be replaced by coniferous species

2.1 Business as usual forest management

The first forest management scenario is the business as usual (BAU) scenario, which will be combined with the BAU land use change scenario (S1). This scenario considers the overall trends in forest management in Flanders and assumes that these trends will continue towards the future. A first important aspect of forest management is the rotation time, indicating at what age a forest stand is felled. Table 5

gives an overview of the rotation times applied for the BAU scenario. These correspond to the standard rotation times already implemented in the Sim4Tree-tool. They are derived from the classical yield tables for the major tree species in the Netherlands and Flanders (Jansen et al., 1996). Sim4Tree makes use of these tables to simulate forest growth.

A second aspect of forest management is species selection for regeneration. Currently in Flanders, species regeneration follows the stand-still principle, which entails that native species cannot be replaced by non-native species and that deciduous species cannot be replaced by coniferous species (Agentschap Natuur en Bos, 2021). This leads to the general and specific regeneration possibilities mentioned in Table 6 and Appendix 1 respectively. Additionally, Flemish forest management favours the use of native deciduous species. Coniferous and non-native forest stands are being converted towards mixed, species rich deciduous forest stands once the stand age reaches rotation time. Sim4Tree gives the option to account for these preferences by allowing the user to assign priorities to the species (Table 7). For the BAU scenario, these principles are taken into consideration.

Additionally, if there are multiple species allowed for regeneration of a felled forest stand, the assignment of a species is based on the suitability of the soil for a species and the provided priority in BAU. Species with a higher suitability for a specific soil will have a higher chance of being chosen for that specific forest stand. Through the provided priorities, this chance can be further increased (priority = 1) or decreased (priority = 3). Both priority and soil suitability are combined to determine the chance of a species being chosen for regeneration from the initial selection of species, which meet the stand-still principle). For examples of this stochastic selection, we refer to [the manual of Sim4Tree](#).

2.2 Nature oriented forest management

The second management scenario is the nature scenario, which will be combined with the SE (S2) and NARA4 (S5) land use change scenarios. This scenario places the focus on biodiversity and nature conservation. The nature management scenario is based on the outcome of a case study on increased biodiversity in Central European forests, which Härkönen et al. (2019) performed. These authors made use of the FORMIT-M open-access forest management simulator (Härkönen et al., 2019). They defined a management strategy which aimed to increase and conserve biodiversity. It differs from our business as usual scenario by (i) increasing the rotation lengths by 25% and (ii) by only regenerating with species belonging to the potential natural vegetation.

The rotation lengths applied in our study are shown in Table 5. In case the rotation length exceeds the maximum age available in the yield table, the latter is taken as the rotation length, thus respecting the limits of the yield tables through which growth is simulated.

In our study, we interpreted the potential natural vegetation as the native species of Flanders. The distinction between non-native and native species is already implemented in Sim4Tree. The current classification was reused for the purpose of this study (Table 7). In the nature oriented scenario, the species selection for regeneration also follows the stand-still principle, just as in the BAU scenario (Appendix 3 Appendix 3: The table shows for each species id by which species it can be regenerated after felling for the nature scenario.). The assignment of a species for regeneration is based on the suitability of the soil for a species and the provided priority of the nature scenario (see 0). For examples of this stochastic selection, we refer to [the manual of Sim4Tree](#).

2.3 Production oriented forest management

The third management scenario is the production scenario, which will be combined with the TA (S3) and NARA3 (S4) land use change scenarios. This scenario prioritises economic interests and wood production. The case of increased harvests for bioenergy in the Nordic countries as elaborated by Härkönen et al. (2019) formed the basis of this management scenario. The production scenario sets the felling age equal to the stand age at which the mean annual increment (MAI) reaches its maximum. The rotation lengths are often shortened in comparison with the BAU scenario. The rotation lengths are dependent on the soil suitability and the species, resulting in a large range of rotation lengths, as fast growing species on very suitable soils will reach their maximum MAI earlier than a slow growing species or the same species on a unsuitable soil. An example of this is pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*), which reaches its MAI after 35 and 120 years on very suitable and less suitable soils, respectively. Based on the yield tables of 2020, each rotation length was manually selected per species per site conditions (Table 5). If the MAI was constant at its maximum value for multiple years, the median stand age was used as the rotation length.

Also in this production oriented forest management scenario, the species selection for regeneration follows the stand-still principle, just as in the BAU scenario (Appendix 4). Whereas no species preferences were set in the case study of Härkönen et al. (2019) which we largely follow, we did define species preferences for the production management scenario. The priorities are presented in Table 7. Highly economically valuable species for the region of Flanders, such as Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) and Beech (*Fagus sylvatica*), received the highest priority. To account for the overall preference towards native and deciduous species, they received the middle priority, while non-native and economically non-important species for Flanders were assigned to the lowest priority. The principle of regeneration for the production scenario is different from that of the BAU and nature management scenario. For the production scenario, species selection is based on the combination of soil type specific species productivity and the regeneration priority. The more productive a species is on a specific soil type, the higher its chances of being chosen for regeneration. Similarly to the BAU scenario, the assigned priority can alter the chance of being chosen at random. For examples of this stochastic selection, we refer to [the manual of Sim4Tree](#).

Table 5: The rotation lengths for the three forest management scenarios and each individual species as derived from the yield tables of 2020 (Storms et al., 2020). The BAU rotation times are those already present within Sim4Tree. The Nature rotation lengths are those of Sim4Tree, but increased with 25%. The Production rotation lengths depends on the soil suitability class (SS), with SS1 begin the best soil suitability and SS5 the worst. The rotation length was determined as the age at which the species reaches its maximal MAI.

Scientific species name	Rotation length (in years)						
	BAU	Nature	Economy				
			SS1	SS2	SS3	SS4	SS5
<i>Abies alba</i>	100	120	40	45	55	60	70
<i>Acer campestre</i>	90	113	30	35	40	50	60
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	90	113	30	35	40	50	60
<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	90	100	15	25	45	60	75
<i>Alnus incana</i>	90	100	15	25	45	60	75
<i>Betula pendula</i>	90	100	15	20	25	35	50
<i>Betula pubescens</i>	90	100	15	20	25	35	50
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	150	150	50	55	65	80	100

Fraxinus excelsior	90	100	30	40	55	70	90
Larix sp.	80	100	30	40	60	75	95
Picea abies	80	90	30	45	55	65	80
Pinus nigra ssp. laricio	90	90	50	70	85	90	90
Pinus nigra ssp. nigra	90	90	80	80	85	90	90
Pinus sylvestris	100	125	40	50	60	75	100
Populus alba	40	50	20	25	25	25	25
Populus canescens	40	50	20	25	25	25	25
Populus nigra var. nigra	40	50	20	25	25	25	25
Populus sp.	40	50	20	25	25	25	25
Populus tremula	40	50	20	25	25	25	25
Pseudotsuga menziesii	100	120	40	45	55	60	70
Quercus petraea	120	150	35	45	55	75	120
Quercus robur	120	150	35	45	55	75	120
Quercus rubra	100	120	35	55	75	100	115
Salix sp.	40	50	20	25	25	25	25
Ulmus sp.	90	100	30	40	55	70	90

Table 6: The stand-still principle describes which type of species can be regenerated by which type after felling .

Current species	Species options for regeneration
native – deciduous	native - deciduous
native – coniferous	native - deciduous, native - coniferous
non-native – deciduous	native - deciduous, native - coniferous, non-native - deciduous, non-native - coniferous
non-native – coniferous	native - deciduous, native - coniferous, non-native - deciduous, non-native - coniferous

Table 7: The priorities assigned to each species when defining regeneration.

Species name	Scientific species name	Native?	BAU	Nature	Economy
Ash	Fraxinus excelsior	Yes	1	1	2
Aspen poplar	Populus tremula	Yes	1	1	2
Beech	Fagus sylvatica	Yes	1	1	1
Common alder	Alnus glutinosa	Yes	1	1	2
Corsican pine	Pinus nigra ssp. laricio	No	3		1
Douglas fir	Pseudotsuga menziesii	No	3		3
Downy birch	Betula pubescens	Yes	1	1	2
Elm	Ulmus sp.	Yes	1	1	2
Field maple	Acer campestre	Yes	1	1	2
Grey alder	Alnus incana	No	2		3

Grey poplar	Populus canescens	Yes	1	1	2
Larch	Larix sp.	No	3		3
Norway spruce	Picea abies	No	3		3
Pendunculate oak	Quercus robur	Yes	1	1	1
Poplar	Populus sp.	No	2		1
Red oak	Quercus rubra	No	2		3
Scots pine	Pinus sylvestris	No	3		1
Sessile oak	Quercus petraea	Yes	1	1	1
Silver birch	Betula pendula	Yes	1	1	2
Silver fir	Abies alba	No	3		3
Sycamore	Acer pseudoplatanus	Yes	1	1	2
Willow	Salix sp.	Yes	1	1	2

3 Implementation in the Sim4Tree Tool

3.1 Spatially explicit afforestation / deforestation

The previous version of the Sim4Tree tool had the option to add pixels dedicated to afforestation at the N1 level (1 ha grid). Such afforestation, however, is not spatially explicit and does not have an exact location in Flanders. Newly created points dedicated to afforestation are in fact copies of existing forest points and their attributes without retaining the coordinates. In order to be as representative as possible, these afforestation points are chosen by the program within the different sub-regions, statutes and soil series in the N1 category. The distribution of points assigned to the different attributes happens proportionally to the existing fractions of forest, located in different regions and attribute groups. In terms of deforestation, there is no real option to delete specific forest points at a certain time. One way is to transform (accelerated conversion or at the end of the (standard) rotation time) a certain species to another land use. As a consequence, no further tree growth and development is simulated in these forest points transformed to other land use.

This random approach is not in line with the five scenarios, which are spatially explicit as they are based on the land use maps of NARA and the VITO world views. Therefore, we expanded Sim4Tree to include the option of deliberately selecting pixels for afforestation and deforestation. For afforestation, the random selection from existing pixels is overruled when a scenario is selected and at each time step new pixels are created at spatially pre-defined locations, which depend on the selected scenario. For deforestation, the felling age of specific pixels is modified, depending on the time step in which the pixel is deforested, and regeneration is inhibited.

3.2 Forest management definition

Sim4Tree has the option to define the type of management for each species individually. Additionally, a variation in management can be made based on region, soil suitability and legal statute of the area (within protected zones or not). This process is, however, time consuming and has to be repeated every time a new scenario is created. If the management scenario is altered by the user, all defined settings can be stored in Sim4Tree as a new scenario and saved for later reuse. Storing a user defined management scenario was already an available functionality of Sim4Tree. Therefore, Sim4Tree has been expanded to include the three distinct management scenarios previously defined: BAU, Nature and Production. This will allow the user to select an overall management goal, which can then be adapted in a faster way.

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5 Appendix

Appendix 1: Species list with species id.

Species name	Scientific species name	Species id
Ash	<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	20
Aspen poplar	<i>Populus tremula</i>	28
Austrian pine	<i>Pinus nigra ssp. nigra</i>	57
Beech	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	2
Black poplar	<i>Populus nigra var. nigra</i>	27
Common alder	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	9
Corsican pine	<i>Pinus nigra ssp. laricio</i>	58
Douglas fir	<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	60
Downy birch	<i>Betula pubescens</i>	13
Elm	<i>Ulmus sp.</i>	51
Field maple	<i>Acer campestre</i>	5
Grey alder	<i>Alnus incana</i>	10
Grey poplar	<i>Populus canescens</i>	26
Larch	<i>Larix sp.</i>	55
Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	56
Pendunculate oak	<i>Quercus robur</i>	34
Poplar	<i>Populus sp.</i>	4
Red oak	<i>Quercus rubra</i>	35
Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	3
Sessile oak	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	33
Silver birch	<i>Betula pendula</i>	12
Silver fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	52
Sycamore	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	7
White poplar	<i>Populus alba</i>	25
Willow	<i>Salix sp.</i>	62

Appendix 2: The table shows for each species id by which species it can be regenerated after felling for the BAU scenario. The species ids are linked to their species names in Appendix 1.

Species ID	Species ID of regeneration																					
	20	58	2	9	58	60	13	51	5	10	26	55	56	34	4	35	3	33	12	52	7	62
20	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
58	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
2	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
9	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
58	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
60	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
13	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
51	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
5	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
10	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	X		X	X
26	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
55	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
56	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
34	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
4	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	X		X	X
35	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	X		X	X
3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
33	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
12	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
52	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
7	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
62	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X

Appendix 3: The table shows for each species id by which species it can be regenerated after felling for the nature scenario. The species ids are linked to their species names in Appendix 1.

Species id	Species id of regeneration																					
	20	58	2	9	58	60	13	51	5	10	26	55	56	34	4	35	3	33	12	52	7	62
20	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
58	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
2	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
9	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
58	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
60	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
13	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
51	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
5	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
10	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
26	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
55	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
56	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
34	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
4	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
35	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
3	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
33	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
12	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
52	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
7	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x
62	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x			x				x	x		x	x

Appendix 4: The table shows for each species id by which species it can be regenerated after felling for the production scenario. The species ids are linked to their species names in Appendix 1.

Species id	Species id of regeneration																					
	20	58	2	9	58	60	13	51	5	10	26	55	56	34	4	35	3	33	12	52	7	62
20	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
58	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
2	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
9	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
58	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
60	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
13	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
51	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
5	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
10	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	X		X	X
26	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
55	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
56	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
34	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
4	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	X		X	X
35	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X	X		X	X
3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
33	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
12	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
52	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
7	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X
62	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X	X

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